

QUANTUM IMAGE PROCESSING FOR FLIGHT SIMULATORS*

Michał KORDASZ, Krzysztof CYRAN

Department of Computer Graphics, Vision and Digital Systems,
Silesian University of Technology, Gliwice, Poland

Introduction

One of the major branches of quantum informatics is image processing. However, quantum computer, because of different construction in comparison to classical computer, requires also different methods to store and process image.

All of the methods of image processing on quantum computer can be divided into two groups. The criterium is the way of encoding the color whether by using one qubit through angle parameter or basis states of a sequence qubits [1].

In this abstract we, the authors, will concentrate only on grayscale methods: **FRQI** [2], **NEQR** [3], **LPIQE** [4]. However, there are methods which expand above mentioned (FRQI and NEQR only) methods for color images (RGB) support. For example, **MCQI** is extended **FRQI** version [5] which supports RGB, so the same is **NCQI**, which implements RGB support and is based on **NEQR**.

FRQI introduced in 2011 was the first method which fully implemented quantum computer power, however not the first at all. The very first method was **Qubit lattice** introduced in 2003 [5] and the concept was fully based on classical image representation, as mentioned before, **Qubit lattice** does not implement quantum computer's advantage.

Materials & methods

The **FRQI** (ab. Flexible Representation of Quantum Images) is a method introduced in 2011. The FRQI is inspired on a method known from classical computers. The quantum state(s) stores information about color (FRQI method is focused for gray-scale images) and pixels' position on image. The main formula, which describes FRQI state is:

$$|I(\theta)\rangle = \frac{1}{2^n} \sum_{j=0}^{2^{2n}-1} (\cos \theta_j |0\rangle + \sin \theta_j |1\rangle) \otimes |j\rangle \quad (1)$$

where: $\theta_j \in \langle 0; \frac{\pi}{2} \rangle$ - angle which codes gray-scale intensity, $j = 0, 1, \dots, 2^{2n} - 1$ - pixels' position.

The second method is **NEQR** (ab. Novel Enhanced Quantum Representation) introduced in 2013. This method requires two entanglement qubits sequences:

- first qubit sequence is used to encode gray-scale level,
- second qubit sequence is used to store pixels' position on image (just as in FRQI).

The main formula, which describes NEQR state is:

$$|I(\theta)\rangle = \frac{1}{2^n} \sum_{j=0}^{2^{2n}-1} (g(j)) \otimes |j\rangle \quad (2)$$

Where: $g(j)$ – is the intensity of the pixel (in gray scale) from 0 to 255, which means values from $|0000\ 0000\rangle$ to $|1111\ 1111\rangle$, $j = 0, 1, \dots, 2^{2n} - 1$ - pixels' position.

The third method, proposed in 2020 is **Local Phase Image Quantum Encoding**. LPIQE uses local phase to encode color of the pixel. It is described by formula:

$$|I\rangle = \sum_{j=0}^J e^{ip_j} |j\rangle \quad (3)$$

Where: $J = \text{height} \times \text{width} - 1$ of the image, p_j – pixel’s intensity, j - pixel

Implementation

All of those methods were implemented by using open-source library Qiskit by IBM. Qiskit is a Python library which provides possibility to create quantum circuits and launch them on different IBM’s quantum computers remotely.

Figure 1: From left: original image, preprocessed image and reconstructed image

As you can see, reconstructed image [Figure 1] is not similar to the original one. It is, because of decoherence of quantum environment. Thus, it is required to implement techniques which will allow for error correction [6].

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